

Analysis of barrier factors getting physiotherapy practises as the emerged therapy, among patient with musculoskeletal injuries in UMM hospital Malang, East Java

Rakhmad Rosadi¹ ABCDEF,

¹Physiotherapy Department University of Muhammadiyah Malang Indonesia

Received: August 20.2016; Accepted: September 12.2016

Abstract

This study aims to analyse the barrier factors that affect on access of physiotherapy practises as the emerged therapy among patient with musculoskeletal injuries in UMM Hospital Malang, East Java. It was conducted through cross sectional study design on 34 respondents who met the inclusion criteria. Two validated questionnaire were used to assess the internal and external barrier of getting physiotherapy practises.

Multiple linear regression were used to analyse the data. The result showed that transportation difficulties, low income and cultural differences were identified by respondents as the most important barrier of getting physiotherapy practises as their emerged therapy for their musculoskeletal injury. Therefore, it suggest increasing the bilingual capabilities of the staff, and enhancing the cultural competency of the providers would reduce barrier to physiotherapy practises

Keywords: Barrier, Physiotherapy practises

Introduction

Musculoskeletal conditions are prevalent and their impact is pervasive. They are the most common cause of severe long term pain and physical disability, and they affect hundreds of millions of people around the world [1]

Musculoskeletal injuries has the highest prevalent among others injuries that need physiotherapy practises in Malang.[2] Health Department of Malang in 2013 reported that within the last five years, its prevalent is increasing 5,3% in each year. Moreover, UMM Hospital, as the biggest hospital which provides physiotherapy practises in Malang, also reported that in 2014 there are at about 50-60 patients with musculoskeletal problems, most of them are patients with ligament , tendon, muscle and overuse injuries. [2]

On the other hand, there is significant problem regarding to the high prevalent of these injuries, since based on the study by Rosadi [2], most of the patient (65%) who came to this clinic were at severe condition and they came after 48 hours of the accident, because when they were at the early stage of getting this injury, they prefer going to alternative clinic rather than going to a physiotherapist. It makes their condition becoming worse and cause complication such as pain, edema, limited for range of motion and infection.

As Bundy and Leaver [3] said that musculoskeletal injury should be treated less than 24 hours after its hap-

pen with PRICED methods (protect, rest, ice, compress, elevation and drugs) to support its recover and prevent from complications.

As Campagne [4] said Serious complications are unusual but may threaten life or limb viability or cause permanent limb dysfunction. Risk of complications is high with open injuries (which predispose to infection) and with injuries that disrupt blood vessels, tissue perfusion, and/or nerves. Dislocations, particularly if not rapidly reduced, tend to have a higher risk of vascular and nerve injuries than do fractures. Closed injuries that do not involve blood vessels or nerves, particularly those that are quickly reduced, are least likely to result in serious complications.

Thus, in this study it will focusing mainly on analyzing the barrier factors that affect on access of physiotherapy practises as the emerged therapy among patient with musculoskeletal injuries in UMM Hospital Malang, East Java.

Material

Population of this study were all of the patients of that have been registered in physiotherapy clinic in UMM Hospital from January until March 2016 . Purposive sampling technique has been used in this study. Therefore, sample used were patients who meets the inclusion criteria, namely: age between 18-31 years old; registered in physiotherapy clinic UMM Hospital from January till

March 2016; diagnosed by having ligament, tendon, muscle and overuse injuries, and have chosen non-physiotherapy practises as their emerged therapy for their injuries. There were 34 respondents that meet with those criteria.

Methods

It was quantitative methodological approach with cross sectional study design. While, questionnaire methods has been used in this proposed study. There were 30 open-ended questions, and it has been validated first before data collection process.

Recruitment and Procedures

It started with getting letter of acceptance and doing ethical study from UMM Hospital as a form of permission to start this research. Then, it continued with medical record study to identify patients who have such ligament, tendon, muscle and overuse injuries and has been registered in physiotherapy clinic from January until March 2016. After sample identified, then it went to recruitment process by contacting patients who met the inclusion criteria and voluntary to be involved in this study as sample. During data collection, each samples has been given two validated questionnaires, which comprises 30 questions, that assessed internal and external barrier factors of getting physiotherapy practises. After data collection finished, then it went to data analysis.

Data Analysis

All of the data collected were analysed using multiple linear regression to know which barrier related on hampering of getting physiotherapy practises as the emerged therapy.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical consideration is applied in this research, since it involves human as a subject of research, and it has two main points, namely focussing on the right of the patients to be treated as openly, not harmed or made comfortable during the research, and making sure that the finding results can be used as accurate decisions for the stakeholders[3].

There are two steps of ethical considerations will be used in this research, namely ethical approval and informed consent. Ethics committee approval obtained from the UMM Hospital Research Ethic Committee, as the data collection site. While, informed consent is consisted of information sheet and consent form. It will inform the participant about the purpose of the study, the participant's role, the voluntary participation means that they can withdraw from the study at any time, the third party contact person for complaints, confirm confidentiality, the

approval of the project by ethics committee, and contact details of the evaluator for questions.

Results

Access barrier of Getting Physiotherapy Practises

Respondents identified several barriers for accessing on physiotherapy practises as their emerged therapy for their injuries in the past. Transportation problems were reported most often (21%). Among the 21 respondents citing transportation problems, the lack of a car was identified as the most frequent difficulty (62%); excessive distance from clinics and the expense or inconvenience of public transportation were also mentioned often. Other frequently cited barriers that had causes respondents choosing the non-physiotherapist as their emerged therapy was included of not being able to afford health care because it was too expensive rather than non-physiotherapist practises (23%), excessive waits to see the physiotherapist (17%), and also more than half of the respondents (59%) were employed, so it affected on inconvenient clinic hours (14%). Then difficulty on making appointments was mentioned by 13% of respondents; spesific difiiculties including excessive waiting time on the telephone when trying to schedule appoinments and excessive intervals until the next available appointments. Some respondents (11%) also mentioned that the physiotherapy clinic located too far away from where they lived. A surprisingly high proportion of respondents said that problems with their culture and belief had caused them choosing on non-physiotherapist practises in the past: 17% mentioned as a cause that physiotherapist, who mostly non-Javanese people, did not understand about respondents' belief of their Javanese culture.

Multivariate Analysis

Based on the Table 9, the result of multivariate linear regression analysis shows that family income, transportation access, and culture were significantly associated with their decision on choosing non-physiotherapist practises for their emerged therapy, since those factors has

P value $< \alpha$ ($\alpha = 0,05$). Yet, respondents' educational level, sex, age and their insurance status were not significantly influenced their decision on choosing non-physiotherapy practises as their emerged therapy since p value $> \alpha$ ($\alpha = 0,05$). From those analysis result, thus it can concluded into formula, namely:

$$Y = 4,73 + 7,62 (\text{Transportation Access}) + 6,81 (\text{Income}) + 5,37 (\text{Culture})$$

Table No 9. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Predicting Barries Factors of Gtting Physiotherapy as Emerged Therapy Among 34 Patients with Musculoskeletal Injuries

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficient (B)	p value
(Constant)	4,73	0,001
Transportation access (X1)	7,62	0,003*
Education level	1,28	0,06
Sex	0,06	0,053
Age	0,087	0,82
Occupation	0,4	0,25
Insurance Status	0,08	0,13
Income (X2)	6,81	0,021*
Culture (X3)	5,37	0,008*

* = significant (p<0,05)

Discussion

Transportation access as barrier of getting physiotherapy services

Transportation is a basic but necessary step for ongoing health care and medication access, particularly for those with musculoskeletal injury. In this study, transportation barriers are an important barrier to physiotherapy access, particularly for those with lower incomes. Many low-income people in urban and suburban areas struggle to find reliable transportation. The result is missed appointments and poor illness management, even when care is readily available. As Syed et al [5] and Cronk [6] said that these consequences may lead to poorer management of musculoskeletal injury and thus poorer health outcomes. Patients with transportation barriers carry a greater burden of disease which may, in part, reflect the relationship between poverty and transportation availability [5,7,8]. Silver et. al [9] found that 25 % of missed appointments/rescheduling needs were due to transportation problems and bus users were twice as likely to miss their appointments compared to car users

Furthermore, supporting with our result that distance affect the utilization of physiotherapy practises, there were two studies by Littenberg et.al [10] and Strauss et. al [11] stated that there were significance relationship that longer driving distances from one's physician are associated with less insulin use or poorer glycemic control independent of social, clinical or economic factors. However, on the contrary, there were one study by Lamount et al. [12] found that a longer distance

to one's health care facility was associated with improved health care access.

Income as Social Determinant of Health

Based on the results, it shows that income can be identified as one of the barrier of getting physiotherapy practises as the emerging therapy. Most of the patients, who have low income, did not choose physiotherapy practises as their emerged therapy for their musculoskeletal injuries, but they rather choose non-physiotherapy practises such as traditional treatment called "sangkal putung" because they thought that it much cheaper than physiotherapy services. DeVoe [13] said that there are three major barriers of getting health care services, namely: lack of insurance coverage, poor access to services and unaffordable costs. Based on the research by Baez [14] and Edlund [15] stated that cost were most often mentioned by family with private insurance as the barrier of health care and even families with health insurance had trouble affording the co-pays as well as needed medications. Moreover, even with service from physicians and expanded coverage of the health insurance, people who have low income are not guaranteed access to health care services [16, 17]. The reasons of this association are not clear. It may arise from limited access to care for people of the working poor, who have often difficulty in obtaining health insurance for their families, and who earn too much to qualify for Medicaid [8]

As WHO [18] stated that income together with other factors such as environment, genetics, education level, and our relationship with family and friends all have considerable impact on health of individuals and community in which higher income were linked to better health care services, and the greater the gap between the richest and the poorer the greater differences on accessing health care.

Culture as barrier of getting physiotherapy practises

As mentioned before, cultural differences has been categorized as one of the barrier of the patients accessing physiotherapy practises as their emerged care. Although only 17 % of respondents cited cultural differences as the single greatest barrier to physiotherapy practises, about 1 in 9 respondents said that it was caused by the physiotherapist did not understand their Javanese culture. Cultural misunderstanding between patient and physiotherapist has created poor awareness of physiotherapy practises. Many people are not aware of physiotherapy centres in their locality or are not aware of the aim of physiotherapy to bring about independence for patients and their families. Moreover, caused by cultural misunderstanding between them, it could contribute to poor quality of care and patient dissatisfaction [19].

However, we did not have the opportunity to identify the specific cultural differences that they perceived as access barriers. However, normative cultural values that can affect clinical care has been identified among Javanese people, including concept of “sopan lan ngregani” [20 21]. In *sopan*, a value is placed on politeness, pleasantness, in the face of stress, and avoiding hostile confrontation [20,21]. Because many Javanese people therefore expect the physiotherapist to have positive attitude, the relatively neutral attitude of many physiotherapist may be perceived negatively. Then, in *ngregani* concept, Javanese patients view physiotherapist as authority figures to be awarded respect, and expect reciprocal respect from the physiotherapist, particularly if the physiotherapist is younger than the patients [21]. Failure of the physiotherapist to use terms of respects and elicit the patient’s concerns can results in negative perception and dissatisfaction of care.

Conclusions

In conclusion, transportation difficulties, low income and cultural differences were identified by respondents as the most important barrier of getting physiotherapy practises as their emerged therapy for their musculoskeletal injury. Some Javanese respondents reported taht the lack of Javanese-speaking physiotherapist resulted in adverse health consequences for them, such as inappropriate treatment, adn misdiagnosis. Thus, they prefer to choose non-physiotherapy care as their emerged therapy. Then, low income emerged from multivariate analysis as an important predictor of suboptimal health and high utilization of health service. Our findings suggest that intervention that would reduce barrier to physiotherapy practises in UMM Hospital might include increasing the bilingual capabilities of the staff, and enhancing the cultural competency of the providers.

References

1. Woolf AD., Pflieger B. *Burder of Majormusculoskeletal Conditions*, bulletin of the WHO, 2003; pp.646-656.
2. Rosadi R. *Profil Pelayanan Pada Pasien Pasca stroke di Poli Fisioerapi RS UMM*, Penelitian Internal DPPM, UMM, 2013;
3. Bundy M., Leaver A. *A Guide To Sport And Injury Management*, Elsevier Ltd, China, 2010;
4. Campagne, Donald MD. *Overview of Fractures, Dislocations, and Sprains*, viewed 14th December
5. <http://www.merckmanuals.com/professional/injuries-poisoning/fractures-dislocations-and-sprains/overview-of-fractures-dislocations-and-sprains> , 2014, 2015
6. Syed L., Schye P., Partida S. Language Differences as a Barrier to Quality and Safety in Health Care: The Joint Commission Perspective, *Journal of General Internal Medicine*, vol. 22, no. 2
7. Cronk M. Development of Operational Strategies for On Demand meal Delivery in healthcare, *IIE Annual Conference Proceedings*, 2013;
8. Wallace L., Lesko S., Angier S. The Effects of Health Insurance and a Usual Source of Care on a Child’s Receipt of Health Care, *Journal of Pediatric Health Care*, 2005; vol.26, no. 5
9. Flores G., Abreu M., Olivar MA., Kastner M. Access Barrier to Health Care for Latino Children, *Archpediatric Medical Journal*, 1998; vol. 152.
10. Silver D., Blustein J., Weitzman Z. Transportation to Clinic : findings from a pilot clinic based-survey of low income suburbanities, *Journal of Immigrant and Minority Health*, 2012; vol. 14, no. 2.
11. Littenberg L., Maclean CD. Literacy and health outcomes a cross sectional study in 1002 adults with diabetes, *BMC Family Journal*, 2006; vol. 7, no.49
12. Strauss L., Krahn GL., Hammond A. A cascade of disparities : health and health care access for people with intellectual dissabilities, *Development Disabilities Research reviews*, 2006; vol. 12, no. 1
13. Lamont D., Parker L., Cohen M., White M., Bennett S., Unwin N., Craft A., Alberti K. 2003, Early life and later determinants of adult disease: a 50 year follow-up study of the Newcastle Thousand Families cohort. *Public Health*, 2003; 12, 85–93
14. DeVoe J., Baez A., Angier H., Krois L. Insurance + Access ≠ Health Care: Typology of Barriers to Health Care Access for Low-Income Families, *Journal of Annals Family Medicine*, 2004; vol. 5, no. 6.
15. Baez JE. Civil wars beyond their borders: The human capital and health consequences of Hosting Refugees. *Journal of Development Economics*, 2011; vol. 96, no. 2.
16. Edlund MJ. Trends in use of opioids for chronic non-cancer pain among individuals with mental health and substance use disorders: the TROUP study, *Clinical Journal Pain*, 2011; vol.26, no. 1
17. Vivier, PM, Health care utilization by children with chronic illnesses, *Archpediatric Medical Journal*, 2005; vol. 116, no. 6.
18. Wang PS., Berglund PA., Olfson M., Kessler RC. Delays in Initial treatment contant after first onset of mental health disorder, *Health services research*, 2004; vol. 39, no.2.
19. WHO Social Determinants of Health <http://www.who.int/social_determinants/en/> accessed on 7th September, 2016;
20. Almutairi K., Culture and language differences as a barrier to provision of quality care by the health workforce in Saudi Arabia, *Saudi Medical Journal*, 2015; vol. 36, no. 4.
21. Dewi F., Weinehall L., Ohman A. Maintaining balance and harmony: Javanese perceptions of health and cardiovascular disease, *Global Health action*, 2010; vol.3, no.10
22. Purwadi *Pranata sosial jawa* Yogyakarta: Cipta Karya, 2007;

Corresponding Author:

Rakhmad Rosadi
e-mail: rakhmad21@gmail.com

Conflict of interest:

The authors have declared no conflict of interest.